

Using Machine Learning to Predict Cancer Rates in Mongolia Over the Past Five Years

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ABSTRACT

The study describes the cancer incidence in Mongolia in the last five years, using machine learning cluster analysis to classify and calculate the different groups of aimags, capital cities, and regions. The study data includes the incidence data of 21 aimags and capital cities in accordance with the zoning of Mongolia in the last 5 years. When the data was divided into 10 clusters using machine learning cluster analysis, the incidence in clusters 3 and 5 was found to have similar values and was regionally related. The provinces in cluster 8 have similar incidence rates and appear regionally dependent. Therefore, we can propose and apply this research work to develop an assessment model that can be used by medical workers, decision-makers in the field and researchers to create a disease assessment with regional, local, provinces, and capital city classifications, and to monitor and evaluate activities.

KEYWORDS: Cancer, Machine Learning, Cluster analysis, HCPC (PCA)

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I. INTRODUCTION

The third goal of Mongolia's "Sustainable Development Vision-2030" is to "Improve the quality and accessibility of medical care, services and reduce mortality rate in cardiovascular disease to 16, reduce cancer rate to 9 per 10,000 population." [4] The law on public health care services was adopted at the meeting of the Parliament on January 12, 2024 [5]. The law, which will come into effect on April 1, 2024, will intensify efforts to protect the health of the population, prevent diseases, and provide health education to citizens. Therefore, we are initiating a fundamental research project on the study of the brain in Mongolia. This study used artificial intelligence software, machine learning methods and techniques to estimate cancer rates in Mongolia over the past five years. The study will continue.

The cancer incidence rate as of 2022 [6]

Table 1. National Statistics Office of Mongolia (NSO)

Leading Malignant Neoplasms, Mongolia (2022)			
	Male	Female	
Liver cancer	35.4%	30.8%	Liver cancer

Stomach cancer	22.1%	11.7%	Stomach cancer
Lung and bronchus cancer	11.1%	9.7%	Cervical cancer
Esophageal cancer	5.4%	8.6%	Breast cancer
Colorectal cancer	4.0%	4.9%	Colorectal cancer
Pancreatic cancer	3.5%	4.5%	Esophageal cancer
Kidney cancer	3.1%	3.7%	Lung and bronchus cancer
Brain and nervous system cancers	2.0%	3.7%	Kidney cancer
Leukemia	1.7%	3.6%	Ovarian cancer
Prostate cancer	1.4%	3.0%	Pancreatic cancer
Newly diagnosed cancer cases (2022)			
	3604	3281	

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II. METHODOLOGY

Data collection: The data were obtained from the National statistics office using the dataset titled “New cancer cases by region, province and the capital city.”

Including: The status of the last five years, 2019-2023

Table 2. Machine learning training dataset

Aimags	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Bayan - ulgii	12.7	11.7	13.7	14.8	15.4
Govi - altai	25.6	21.2	19.6	23.1	28
Zavkhan	22.3	20.3	22.3	23.1	26
Uvs	24.7	24	21.3	24.1	29.3
Khovd	20.8	17.8	18.5	24.5	23.1
Arkhangai	21.9	17.4	18.4	31.7	28.3
Bayankhongor	16.5	16.9	15.2	17.1	19.4
Bulgan	20.3	17.7	18.1	21	38
Orkhon	20.7	28.9	23.4	24.7	23.6
Uvurkhangai	20.4	21.4	21	22.4	25.5
Khuvsgul	22.1	19.5	20.1	22.4	22.7
Govi - sumber	16.7	23.1	11.1	15.5	16.6
Darkh - uul	24.2	21.4	22.5	26.1	27.6
Dornogovi	18.9	19	15.6	17	21.1
Dundgovi	26.6	18.3	20	18.6	15.6
Umnigovi	12.4	15.6	17.2	19.2	20.1
Selenge	28	27.1	20.5	21.9	23.8
Dornod	22.3	24.4	20.7	25	
Sukhbaatar	26.4	20.1	22.5	26.9	22.2
Khentii	33	26.3	20.8	22.3	33.1
UB	15.3	18.9	16.9	18.3	18.2

Method: Cluster analysis HCPC(PCA) method [1-3]

Machine learning: used here (table 1)

Figure 1. Cluster analysis of the set (province, UB)

Machine learning: used here (table 1) Program code: `plot(res.hcpc1, choice = "3D.map")` Results:

Figure 2. Cluster analysis of the set 3D (province, UB)

Here, the selected set (Table 1) is presented in the form of a 3D cluster analysis. The first principal component explains 62.1% of the total variance, and the second principal component explains 15.46% of the variance and this goes down with each component. The last row, the cumulative ratio is calculated by calculating the cumulative sum of the second row.

Software: R, Python programs were used.

III. RESULTS

HCPC(PCA) for cluster analysis – The method of calculating the principal components.

This method allows to check whether each variable of the data (Table 1) is scaled with a mean value of 0 and a standard deviation of 1 before calculating the principal components. To see the difference between the analysis without standardization, the correlation and covariance matrices were generated using the PCA method.

Calculation of the selected set (table 1) Result:

	X2019	X2020	X2021	X2022	X2023	Min.	Min.	Min.	Min.
Min.	:12.40	:11.70	:11.10	:14.80	:15.40				
1st	1st	1st	1st	1st	1st				
Qu.:	Qu.:18.90	Qu.:17.80	Qu.:17.20	Qu.:18.60	Qu.:20.10				
Median	Median	Median	Median	Median	Median				
:	:21.90	:20.10	:20.00	:22.40	:23.60				
Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean				
:	:21.51	:20.52	:19.02	:22.01	:23.93				
3rd	3rd	3rd	3rd	3rd	3rd				
Qu.:	Qu.:24.70	Qu.:23.10	Qu.:21.00	Qu.:24.50	Qu.:27.60				
Max.	Max.	Max.	Max.	Max.	Max.				
:	:33.00	:28.90	:23.40	:31.70	:38.00				

Categorization

The cancer rates for the 2019-2023 period by provinces and capital city according to the regionalization of Mongolia (Table 1) were categorized by cluster analysis and presented in the following table.

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Table 3. Selected categorization

Cluster's number	Aimag and city
Cluster_1	Bayan Ulgii
Cluster_2	Gobi Sumber
Cluster_3	Bayankhongor Dornogobi Umnugobi UB
Cluster_4	Dundgobi
Cluster_5	Zavkhan Khovd Uvurkhangai Khuvsgul
Cluster_6	Bulgan
Cluster_7	Arkhangai
Cluster_8	Gobi Altai Uvs Darkhan-Uul Dornod Sukhbaatar
Cluster_9	Orkhon Selenge
Cluster_10	Khentii

Here (cluster 8) - Gobi Altai, Uvs, Darkhan Uul, Dornod, and Sukhbaatar provinces have similar incidence rates. It is clear that there is no regional correlation here. (Cluster 3, 5) provinces have similar incidence rates in the last 5 years.

CONCLUSIONS

Mongolia's cancer rates for the last 5 years were classified into cluster analysis categories.

1. In (cluster 3), Bayankhongor, Dornogovi, Umnu Gobi, and UB aimags have similar incidence rates. It is observed that the central region is relevant.
2. In (cluster_5), Zavkhan, Khovd, Uvurkhangai, and Khuvsgul aimags have similar incidence rates and are relevant to the western region.
3. In (cluster 8), Gobi Altai, Uvs, Darkhan Uul, Dornod, and Sukhbaatar aimags have similar incidence rates. It is observed that there is no regional relevance.

Therefore, it seems important to classify diseases according to their region. Diseases are becoming more regional. Disease assessment using new technologies, AI and ML methodologies and calculations is producing real results.

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